

Purpose, Protest and Social Reconstruction in the Novels and Short Stories of Maxim Gorky and Thakazhi Sivasankara Pillai

**Dr. Vidya Hariharan,
Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
SIES College of Arts, Science and Commerce,
Sion West, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India.**

***Abstract:** Most of the time when we talk of Russian literature we tend to think of such major writers as Leo Tolstoy, Fyodor Dostoevsky, Gogol, Pushkin, Nabokov or Anton Chekhov. Rarely does the reader think of Maxim Gorky, one of the most prolific Russian writers. Gorky had had a tremendous impact on the thoughts and writings of many Indian writers, one of whom is Thakazhi Sivashankara Pillai, a novelist from Kerala. A comparative study of both these writers will yield rich dividends. Both Maxim Gorky and Thakazhi Sivasankara Pillai lived and worked through some very interesting and tumultuous times in the histories of their regions. Gorky in Russia and Thakazhi in Kerala were at the forefront of nascent political movements and new creative urges that changed the cultural, literary, social and political landscape of their respective regions. In the delineation of their characters and the thematic concerns of their fictional works, whether short stories or novels, the reader can find astonishing parallels. Gorky's revolutionary ideas and Thakazhi's leftist leanings, that emerged from lived experience, and led to a passionate desire to change society for the better, showcases what came to be known as the 'class novel'. Both writers depict workers/peasants as victims of powerful social and political forces but also their desire for transformation. In 'Two Measures', 'The Children of Ousep', 'The Rungs of the Ladder', 'The Scavenger's Son' and 'The Rope' Thakazhi describes the lives of the*

downtrodden in Kerala using a simple style and the language of the common man; just as in 'Foma Godeyev', 'Chelkash', 'The Artomonovs', '26 Men and a Girl' and 'Mother' Gorky lays out his vision for a better Russia. Both authors worked at a time of turbulence and change, and utilized the literary form for social awareness and social rebuilding. This paper attempts to explore the similarities and differences in the style and themes of select fictional works of Gorky and Thakazhi in order to get a better understanding of how these writers' beliefs in building a better society through the authors' contribution bore fruit in both Russia and Kerala.

Keywords: Thematic concern, Style, Social awareness, Class novel.

“However thick this layer (of beastly brutalities) may be, bright, healthy and creative things can nevertheless break through it; fine human seeds grow nevertheless, fostering an imperishable hope of our re-birth to a brighter, truly human life.”

(Gorky qtd in Lukacs 1978, 190)

The words quoted above are Maxim Gorky's but they might have been spoken by Thakazhi too. Alexei Maximovich Peshkov, born in Tsarist Russia and Thakazhi Sivasankara Pillai, well known as Thakazhi, born in Kerala, might as well have been comrades in arms, where their thoughts and ideas regarding a peasant revolution are concerned.

Thakazhi's roots in a land-owning family gave him a unique insight into the life of the farmers who worked in the Alleppey district of Kerala, especially the Kuttanad area, once known as the rice-bowl of the state. His father, Sankara Kurup, was trained in the art form of Kathakali but considered his profession to be that of a farmer. After completing high school, Thakazhi wandered around without purpose for two years. In the end he decided to enroll in the Law College in the capital city, Trivandrum. During this period

he came into contact with the intelligentsia in the city, especially the great literary critic and editor of the 'Kesari' A Balakrishna Pillai. It is he who introduced Thakazhi to the modern European writers like Chekhov, Tolstoy, Maupassant, Zola and Gorky. It was at this time, during the 1940s that the Progressive Writer's movement was influencing all of Kerala and Thakazhi was in the midst of this movement. The period from 1930 to 1947 came to be known as the era of Social Realism in Malayalam literature. During this period literature became truly democratic. Stories which were true to life, characters who were representatives of certain communities or classes, simple and direct language were some of the chief characteristics of this fiction. The purpose was social awakening and renewal. Both Gorky and Thakazhi championed the cause of the underdog. They had a deep knowledge of contemporary life that demanded the righting of long-standing wrongs. The very structure of society is attacked by these two authors. Thakazhi has penned over 500 short stories and 35 novels and each of these tales speaks of the unremitting exploitation, the struggle for survival and the desire to overcome the circumstances of their birth that some classes are doomed to suffer. The characters are drawn from the lowest rungs of society- Two Measures is about the life of the landless peasants in Kuttanad, the Scavenger's Son is about three generations of scavengers in Alleppey, and Kayar (The Rope), which many critics consider as Thakazhi's magnum opus is a chronicle of the rise and fall of several landowning families with the changing political and social climate in Kerala over a period of 250 years.

Gorky's wanderings around Russia brought him into contact with the suffering populace of his country and the people he met during this period enriched his fiction and, moreover, gave greater verisimilitude to his characterization. The repressive measures of the Tsarist regime of over 300 years had robbed the peasants of their dignity. Both Thakazhi and Gorky realized the importance of restoring that lost dignity and rebuilding the damaged psyche of their people. Social reconstruction was the need of the hour and both the writers knew that portraying the true picture of the

downtrodden would make the readers aware of the misery and exploitation occurring in their midst. Also the need to educate the masses themselves that the pathetic conditions in which they were living were not immutable was realized by both writers.

In *Scavenger's Son* Thakazhi describes the miserable lives of three generations of scavengers in Alleppey. These scavengers are socially ostracized, they are exposed to infections and epidemics, they are cheated by their superiors as they do not know how much they earn, and their children are denied schooling.

In *Two Measures*, set in Kuttanad, ironically, the rice granary of Kerala, Thakazhi portrays the life of the Parayas – the agricultural serfs. They are ignorant, superstitious and loyal to their landed masters. Their loyalty is rewarded with severe thrashings for the smallest misdemeanors. If the master does show some sympathy for them it is merely that of an owner towards his possession and not a recognition of mutual brotherhood.

Beggar Class is an exploration of the origin of the beggars who are seen on the city streets. The author depicts the life of two such families who are reduced to begging to keep body and soul together as they lost their property. These beggars, he tells us, were once workers and peasants till their health fails irretrievably and because of the neglectful attitude of the State and the Capitalists who do not offer these unfortunates any protection, they fall into despair and become invisible in society.

Children of Ousep and Rungs of the Ladder are harsh critiques of the new capitalists. According to Thakazhi they have lost their moorings from tradition but have failed to retain any strong relational bonds within their own family or society. He is critical of their complacency in the midst of plenty. The author highlights this condition by describing the life of Mannan in *Children of Ousep*. He had experienced grinding poverty but manages to become very wealthy. He then proceeds to kill his younger brother to appropriate his property and sends another brother into the Seminary against his wishes. Thus financial improvement is

accompanied by moral degradation due to the avarice and ego of the capitalists or muthalali.

Maxim Gorky was born during the dawn of tumultuous change in Russia, when the soil was fertile for a revolution, the necessity of which Gorky believed in absolutely. The condition of the peasants had not improved materially even after the Emancipation reforms of 1861, which abolished serfdom; they were forced to pay a number of taxes and pay rent for using grazing lands and watering holes which was under the control of the landlord. Hunger was their perennial companion. In 1861 there were more than 4 million landless peasants. Another significant aftermath of the reforms was the growth of non-gentry private land ownership. Since gaining independence from the British, several land reforms were sought to be put into practice, the most famous among which was the Land Reform Act which caused a terrific uproar among the land owning community of Kerala. The ordinance set an absolute ceiling on the amount of land a family could own. The tenants and hut dwellers received a claim in the excess land, on which they had worked for centuries under the feudal system. In addition, the law ensured fixity of tenure and protection from eviction. But the historical land reform act, Kerala Land Reforms (Amendment) Act, 1969 which put an end to the feudal system and ensured the rights of the tenants on land, came into force on 1 January 1970. The slogan of the socialists in Kerala was “the land for tillers”. The land reforms in Kerala imparted drastic changes to the political, economic and social outlook, as in Russia. So, in both Russia and Kerala there was the simultaneous existence of the traditional wealthy land owning community which was slowly but surely losing power, an emergent class of landowners who benefitted from the land reforms and through sheer hard work managed to buy arable land who were on an economic upswing, and the landless tenant farmers. Both Gorky’s and Thakazhi’s tales are drawn from this unfortunate section of society. And both are extremely critical of the new capitalists. Thakazhi’s *The Rope* and Gorky’s *The Artomonovs* share a similar theme.

“Why should man thirst for earth? Why this love? Leave the earth alone. Let what the earth produces be for all” (The Rope, 925).

These words are echoed by Pavel in *Mother*:

“We are revolutionaries and will be...as long as private property exists, as long as some merely command and as long as others merely work” (365).

So the work of both Gorky and Thakazhi reflects a purposeful writing. Although not overtly a socialist, Thakazhi’s leftist leanings ensured a sympathetic view of the downtrodden in his fiction. Not as strident as Gorky, his works reveal an obdurate intention to expose the real conditions of people who are invisible to society.

For Gorky, literature acts as a tool to educate people about their condition and to help them rise above it. He was astonished and angered at the acceptance of the workers and peasants towards the crippling conditions of their lives. Gorky takes on the role of spokesperson to make the workers realize the dignity of their labour. His early works like *Makar Chudra* and *Old Izergil* explore the concept of freedom, are romantic in style and have some semi-legendary heroes. But, eventually, he realized the limitations of gaining a personal freedom and aims for ‘class’ freedom. This realization is accompanied by a change in the stories he narrates and the characters which populate them as seen in *Twenty six Men and A Girl*. The men laboring under filthy conditions in the bakery idealize the beauty and innocence of a girl who often visits the bakery to buy bread. Unfortunately their ideal fails when she is seduced by a man they consider no better than them. The author’s reasoning is that the worker has to look deep within himself for the redemptive force rather than rest his hopes on any external agency. Similar themes are explored in *Cheklash* and *Konovalev*, which are populated with ordinary people whom the peasants and workers can identify with.

Education is seen as a tool for social change by both authors. In *The Scavenger's Son*, Mohanan, the scavenger's son is admitted as a student, after the payment of a bribe. *Scavenger's Son* and *Mother* showcase the awakening of the revolutionary spirit among the people. An earlier generation simply accepted atrocities committed on them as part of their fate, their children became aware of the miserable conditions of life but tried to escape this consciousness and their helplessness through alcohol or attempted individual liberation, however, it is the third generation which is the harbinger of revolutionary change. They recognize the need for the workers to unite under a single banner. Pavel and Mohanan are at the forefront of this struggle. In *Scavenger's Son* Mohanan leads a procession of workers on the streets "The next day it was he who was leading the procession that was going through the important parts of town. The crowds of participants were lined up one behind the other in two ranks. In front Mohanan stood carrying a large flag. Long live the revolution! That cry broke the walls of the heavens. They began a battle song that would give renewed energy. Keeping in step with the rhythm the procession moved off. The flag was fluttering in the breeze. The crowd, unarmed and possessed only spiritual strength, moved forward under the leadership of the scavenger's son." (142).

In *Mother* Pavel and his friends organize the May Day demonstration to test the workers solidarity.

"Pavel lifted his arm and the banner wavered, a dozen hands grasped the smooth white wood of the flagstaff, and among them was the hand of the mother. Long live the working class! cried Pavel. Hundreds of voices roared back in response... The crowd grew. Pavel lifted the banner and it unfolded in the air as he carried it forward..." (171).

In both novels the procession is not allowed to move further by the appearance of reactionary forces, in one, the army, in the other, the police. There is not only the realistic portrayal of struggle but the criticism of a society that continues to validate the status quo.

At the heart of all their work was a belief in the inherent worth and potential of the human person. The revolutionary humanism of Gorky influenced Thakazhi in his writings; they do not hold individuals at fault for their trials and tribulations or even for their wickedness, but consider the social structure to be at fault. Although most of their characters never attain happiness in their personal lives, this does not make their works pessimistic. Instead there is a hope for redemption and a better future for society as a whole.

In the words of Gorky, “Life is always surprising us, the creative human powers of goodness...awaken our indestructible hope that a brighter better and more humane life will once again be born” (1).

What is the relevance of these two writers today who are clubbed under the banner of social realists?

In the increasingly atomistic life led by individuals in the globalized world a certain way of life described by these two writers – a community-based life, a celebration of human relationships and the need for struggle could echo once again in individual minds and reawaken a genuine interest in humanity. Both the writers have created narratives reflecting the socio-political contexts of their times without romanticising those living conditions. Gorky's literature addresses pre-revolutionary and revolutionary Russia, while Thakazhi's writings address mid-20th century Kerala society.

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